

7
TRAN
D. G. K. S. 30

M. E. PRICKETT
1574 EASTON Rd
WARRINGTON, PENNSYLVANIA 18976
DEPT. OF ANTHROPOLOGY
PEABODY MUSEUM
HARVARD UNIVERSITY
CAMBRIDGE MASSACHUSETTS
02138

✓
0
3

D17 D18 = Borog

Stems. QALATU. Slender 199 (1)

130 paces across. + c 360m ^{4R} long
goes up to c 20m from the sea
+ bounded on other edge by prominent
low ridge it shows a subtle
rocky sloping site
wall lines visible ~~with~~ rough
stones lots of coral rock, ~~no~~ gatch
some wall line gatch and also floor.
~~no~~ gatch plaster but wall has not
gatched.
sand dunes blowing over seaward edge.

1 dbou = Zarat harbour.

360 LR + 90 paces to end

90 faces east of late + early

late buildings walls standing, rocks
coral rubble. buildings 70 x 140
center 100 faces through road
debris continues

at x small boats (1 row) + nets
+ a small used shelter.

N end of site is

LR from village

ru modern stuff - much modern
area.

Modern walls starting up to 1 1/2 m.

2c picked up by netla all on
~~area~~ area. is in later
than 2B which is from walled
area but does include none
for ~~area~~ area is 18c
Chaveseine like top.

→ present use none. but present
fishing + coypus c b.
no water.

35 x max speed 80
 c ~~the~~ (ests) mud snail
 a little veg. v. low plants
 sheltered by large rock at W of Shwin
 bay from Shermal. sandy.

present use net mending nets ~~to~~
 20ft long anchored. + 2 small cages

no real mounding what top of
 tray beach cliff c ~~to~~ height

SHIWU I learn 10% ^{D 15} to village

v few nests vesting out of sand

~~to~~
 you could bring walkways over the bay.

see H W. Warner JBS 1864/55
 186790

Portuguese fort, SHIWU. 2.
 400 x 300 ^{ft} ~~train~~ mound.
 creek little boats went up + down
 no rays Cathuda.

D 16

5. Qadi water here was.
 ?? centing??

stone outside he says was lighthouse.

be clear 1000 feet line here.
 fort in top 19c.

c 50 scrubby palm trees
 lots of good well water
 30-50 wells

best use of road is berkelee
 hole, 1 house & bathroom on part.
 on side of road to Sperral.

bears 150° to village
 which begins at the end of the road

D14

7

~~STH~~ MOGHUN(S) 1A + 1B.

bears 100° to village c 1k off.

runs up to creek on side of.

32 x 12 oyster mounds - not continuous
 some real piles. then beside other shells
 on point between 2 mounds = 1B.

+ PALMS

at W end of bay. low stone mounds
me $\frac{3}{4}$ m.

2 main lot matters ~~at the bottom~~
quite a good hat between.
palm trees c 30-40 dm -
Sandy wash.
vegetation v sparse scrub. water
= river fast palm trees.

210m quite LR + 70ert.

small scatter +
some shell midden
not oyster.

100m. wash - Mounding of
rain site. ~~at~~ Litman head
of road begins after ~~c.~~ c. 80m

1 oyster midden 3 faces up.

450^{LR} from wadi.
~~270~~ 270 across under A font-
ory by 200m mounding.
site goes to beach

~~270~~ c 4 1/2 m. check

extends beyond Wadi covered by town.
~~5~~ 5 m ht

~~270~~ site D. 300 + 250 m LR est

well beyond town site does not
reach it

22. $\square$ 0 1 = $\frac{1}{5}$ up.

fish in connected whole
unpolluted oysters when water
debraunches

oysters 30 + 13 pps

\$ flat + rot v concentrated
only zone v weather better (less)
modern

010

11

NERAN ①. beam. & 115° to house
ground place marked on map

\$ Stone, rises c 1.5 m above
beach rock dash.

some patch used, but generally
lot. all built ~~corally~~ beach rock.
hard stone

no water but some coconuts a palm
& another tree - one otherwise
uninhabited.

shells but no oysters -
counted stuff, 400 on inside quite
quite reasonable to cross but ridge
at ~~250m~~ 900m from house
at $\frac{1}{2}$ way down into

1 hut on a mound goats beside 2 trees
place where water drops dramatically
but MKS belt worn thin + left knee
on sea very small

oyster mounds $\int 200 \times 20.5$
 $70 \times 10 / + 70 \times 20.5$
also older one 30×15 (NERAN
2) D11

big piles on beach roden
& also on top of flat rocks
dead, roden big piles but
among pottery much more

ventless + more one much more
ventless

hears 275° to building, $\approx 300m$

From the pottery, all
water worked comes down the beach
from by Neran I

oyster mounds $100 + \del{20}$ 20

$\frac{1}{10}m$ area a little
200m along in not work

NERAN B2 only. 3 mounds kept

200m or 10x10 oysters
+ 25x3m (est) roughly fort
with NERAN 2. + further 10x10 of oysters

294. 2 houses + a 14 face
under long oblong

oyster middens around houses
100 + 80 faces by forward
house on top
I think this is ~~THE~~ NERAN

just before wadi on reef. 012

NERAN 3. 360 + 160 faces
stone walls no coral. Muggs off + c.
50 40m from shore which is
narrow stretch scrub veg + road
dunes before coast.
no gatch, lots of ~~oysters~~ ^{faces}
stone walls

NERAN 4 160 + 160 faces.

013

160 + 160 by stadel ~~100m~~
c 30m ht + ht ~~100m~~ 100m
is used x c 30m with masonry + gatch
wall has etc around lots of fort.

on top of fort modern shelters +
1/2 way up to 2 oyster working
cases - oysters have eroded from
there + mixed with holes = 2
shells 15 + 20 + 20 + 20 faces

c 300m beyond is 40x25
oysters on coast.

above 3 little gashed walls on rock
ledge c 10 m up.

Wadi between 2 mts is c 300 m

~~leave 3 at 29.55 = 2.4 hrs~~

~~broken base (42) 32.05~~

~~1st start 32.65~~

~~Wadi 35.43 = .88~~

~~2nd start 38.00 = 38.12 ^{35.77}~~

~~Mogham 39.05. stop 39.65~~
~~- 40.05~~

~~end of Mogham 40.45~~
~~SHIWA 47.2~~

Mogham

village seems to have 3 wells + 3
interris.

end of Mogham 1.8 hrs to SHIWA
start of town.

Wadi with oysters is $3\frac{1}{4}$ hrs from
end of Mogham.

Near I is 6.4 hrs (for end) from
Mogham.

The II is 6

The broken base near 2 is 600 m further
Near 3 is 9.4 hrs (near end) to Mogham.

Mogham - Near the coast, the
ridge is very sharp steep + virtually
unbroken.

^{wells}
 ↓
 ZIARAT + beyond it just before Wadi
 on map in BOROG-LA. large
 Stein p. 199. Site.
 2 reservoir modern on rear of site

site is 500m + 145 faces,
 80m to Zarat side in flat ground

width 270 faces to ridge D18
 then 170 to big ridge
 with castle c 35-40m up
 + 120 faces + 20.

ZIARAT. C is around this

site reaches up to wadi + beyond it
 just sand.

A collected by Mortha + Me

D19

here is from Zarat side +
 also from rear of site mine from
 wadi + front

good gathered walls spec: B
 a good wadi section as: Siraf.

c 5 1/2 m 2t

ZIARAT. D. in oases wadi
 est. 30 x 20 in sand. little flat
 between 2 ridges.

c 600 m on are 5 wells c
 10 fulwars + rod, oyster shells
 with oysters c ~~100~~ x 40; roadline
 on spread out of wadi
 + ~~at~~ another 5 x 5 on the side.

BOROG-LA 2, nearer to shore
 oysters c 200 x 30 weathering
 out of crop. site c 300 x 50 faces
 spreading down due

were files mostly just matter

56.85
57.1 → 750

B-D center 57.6
start BA 57.85 → BOROGGA I
end BA 58.45
mid Zarat 60.3
start 61.17

BOSTANU(S) I.
has 1750 + c 600 men from village
sporadic herds.
size est 60 x 40 m.

BOSTANU(S) 3 on spit on Zarat
side of village D22

400 x 180 feet est.
+ c 75 cows high rocks along
road no water

BOSTANU(S) 2 around
village road dunes + to
E of village c 250 x 200 m

1 m before well origin of well or
cistern

on other side of wall

$\frac{1}{2}$ faced by M.
↓

craters 40×30 + (50×15) . few
were just as usual - vesic +
mass of construction with four gatch

If we return to B check distance
from garden part

Bagh - Buraid on N small mound.

Tal = PARQU 2 a trap trap c 600
m on bearing 325° to Parqu.
c 75 m + 20 + 25 m ext
a little trap.
surroundings as Parqu I.

Tal - PARQU Stein mound
still called that c 25-30 ft ht
faced by Martha 287 x 176.

bearing 185° to Darhti. + c c 90
to Bagh - Buraid (not visible - trap)
surroundings, arable fields, soft earth
mound was cut. lots of candle sticks
not picked up - ~~all~~ traces of
some batch + 1 floor. 1 little
mound c 5 m sq was not cut

c 2 ft + Mud brick hemlock elder

Parque 3. rare surrounding bears
3 50° + c. ~~127~~ m from

Parque
2 trees with

Parque 3 303 + 237
c 4 m ht. | 118 - 120 + 6 (M)
field c 2 m ht

→ walking on bears 270°

bearing taken from +

(4) 2 roads with saddle with field
+ roads between

at c 150m from main mound.

field between 1 + 2 to back

estimate of bear $\frac{1-4}{404} = 2 \cdot 10^0$

stop 30 - start 12 stop 209

from 3 going on bears 90° for 3

not a lot of kind on other sides
but - with 3.

(5)

542 on bears 110°
x 184

245° to main mound + c 100 paces
at 80 to high mound
25 to (7).

small road 46 + 44 paces 16 + 18 m
or walls 10 paces thick thick
or thick whitish patch rubble
~~stone between~~ no face seen

put - Paragraph.

quite a bit of pot bit for studs
to pick up - on top level
floor to be by the base on outside

8 2 + 61. 32 for, bet rent +
are further out 4 passes sq. needs.

good bit of needs not V
diagnostic
PAROV. ?

to 5-7. fields.

5 is softish earth no is ?

ht 5 - 2 1/2

ht 6 - 4m.

ht 7 - ~~2m~~ 2?

distance 8 - 6. est
distance 7 - 6 est
+ bearing est 100°

Beh Oel

stone streaked with iron
underneath a slaty shuff and cracks
Konardur - Beh Deh - ~~Pad~~

Baukehut

Tang i Parah

3 or 4 months 15-20-1 month.

- He M5 we heat round
↔

everyone put the men

like a head oven. paid

buy it.

30-40 at a time women made it.

last year

3-4 months time - Talbertan

~~300~~ ~~300~~ 300 pots

every day 2-3,

only 40 days

sentin of work

Beh Oel

clean cover that wood date may
fire

make a hole wood date dry
cover with wood

fire size
now rate fainted & some do not
not no much demand
only Beh Oel

in bank the rate handle bubble

3-400 years

asking mother + father

He M5 The July August
after date harvest.

brush wood September August
He M5 Sahmar or Nehuf

Beh Deh

Morning take it out

10-12 hrs / 30-40 pots at a

Tang : Bandar - Cavaballe

Port Pakel - + on by sea

to Uledar

Bidukun & canal lit donkey
better

from Beh deh Donkey to Uledar

lit as donkeyable not by canal

4 feet fat

ask train

only one for tang

body Kheze

1 with 3 3 for ride for each

Barokher + Kharviny v close

Porlog

Q 15

Tefe BIKAR (RUDAN) I

on terrace beside rd S from Bikar
and brick on stone foundation
~~still~~ still standing a bit galek
like but small structure with little
+ late pot c 25m apart.

lt of mound occupation c 3m apart
just before village ~~at~~ of Dek
GILKHAM. to left of rd

T. BIKAR 2. ~~RUDAN~~

Q 16

on terrace beside Rd S from
Bikar. stone wall lines on
terrace to rt of rd.

by houses. 70 x 40.

est ~~50~~ 500m this is
on other side of village

Q 17

(+) 33

MAURUM

T MAURU Andon Stein mte.

slab on top + W slope north,
W slope

Martha collected slab on top

1100 faces to E.

MAURU

2.

Q 18

(+)

on line to Dalah Kurun bearing
west with Martha

Q 19

Mam 3

Q 20

Mam 4

POT at KRIANSIAHAR

clay comes by donkey on pangs
from near to house c 300m
away on old way led.

left to dry in lumps
then beaten up + rewed.

Then in piddling pit. big lumps
then small.

the sieve is raft can with holes
in bottom.

then on mat under polythene
is stored wet piddled clay.

we run wedges on wooden palette
at the head.

1 man throws in a pit leaves thumb
marks on each pot.

Then it dries up on mats
or on wetted ground via palm
frond cover.

before now wedging be dries it
with little bit of chert stuff.

wedging takes c 4.5 sec to a lump
5.5 50

2 min 7 sec

2 min 5 sec 2 min 5.1

~~2 min 2.5 sec~~
~~2 min 2.5 sec~~
~~2 min 2.5 sec~~
shape. no preparation to wheel.
~~2 min 2.5 sec~~ 30°
1 min.

water beside the man.

holder: front holds 10-12 pots
- lines of 2.

~~40~~ 1m 25
20 to 1m 05

45 with a nose 210.

40 new welds up. 1m 25 legs
min. 210 all finished

from north these
scale the earth

1 old market pots away + for
earth.

150 = admin = 200

150 or 20 a day

24 years all year.

Jaziri Rudan.

another factory over Max
~~day~~ north ~~of~~ 400-500
250 from each

big factory at bar

3 ~~days~~ days

used up ~~all~~ all day under pressure

They ordered the spindle of the ~~wheel~~ wheel.

They hot for 2 days

2 days they got

new clay, large amount today.

left for the night

a home

water with scratched deer
do they make MARG-IL.

NO

they probably only use 1 deer
~~the~~ load of ~~crap~~ day a day

YES

salt on surface of clay -
valmity

do they use deer, crap
beside the clay?

Q 21

39

KUM 12 ①. 50 + 80 paces tall
was ~~larger~~ larger: pit to rt of rd.
palm trees around + jungle
on 1 side.
forest like balustrade.

village of Hums beam, 3500 ft
c 200m.

c 350 m from river

95° - to Qaleh Kunis

137 - to T. MAURU.

dimensions 174 x 352 paces

The latter pots for ~~2 days~~ the te
 is the both be + the ~~at~~ clay separation
 beats resting clay on ash
 then a little pit.

puts it out + flattens
 13:15 - 18:20
 15:15 first coats it with ash
 beat on flat till
 18:15 like bricks put + beats - put.
 20:30 puts it out

13:15 - 18:20 when he puts it out
 + flattens it by hand 19:40

does it with his hands + out
 slats were one 21:10.

see sketch 1940 after 21:10
 24:05 → put it
 sometimes before this decar on ~~the~~ neck
 They are doing it to 5 A
 4 of which have decar. 2705
 2 ⁴ 45 put it out
 at 26 finished

They each put a little ball of clay
 - int + ash inside.
 When does it inside by foot for c
 10 sec.
 earth c 3 cm by ext.

3rd row put around with water
 water pots - ~~the~~ slats ^{kip folds}

getting fingers on bottom from
sliding off the wheel.

~~In the case of the water, the water is
full of water. has water to be used for...~~

prints at: within the first
then covered with crap
from a hand full in.

Tray by hand...

It uses flat leather.

Then uses other kinds, the ark
even 15-20 times

only used once when it's full

but that water, consistent

filled one in the round one

Ch, operator. Puddling put row creek in
polythene
hanging, has boddled.

4 days. then 54 knots here
the 1 day paper
2 days dry

8 days

leave 72 T fill

3 weeks fill a bin 150-200
= a bin

even buys it himself

KARAT. Saw trees
very big from here
~~was~~ no tag here

~~the water one~~

5 people big wood

1 water carrier
2 people carry clay
1 drink a day
2 guys pottery

ark or flour

clay evap is c 4 hrs dry

2 hours to heat
next ~~day~~ take up
to fill 1 hour.

1: inside + 3 outside

Then 3 hours to put on roof

They go fast no storage
or buying

10 man decorated + 5 for plain ones

each firing clay costs.
wood costs

from when people clean yards
+ boughs

5 people 20 loads all

5, = 105 rals - all

people he has 20m by
wedding
~~to the top of 20m by that time~~
~~1,000 for 2 or 3 months~~

2 loads a day
under ground the day day
~~day~~

wedding 1 man. water pots
one man hits out

[water 3 days a fin.
wedger 12 days]

The pot he has is 176 + 54
is more than 1 ~~pair~~ of beinful

[taught by father who is dead,
work will not die, son is small]

it is owned by the one who owns the
other
fatter road same, with one tool

~~to~~ tie decorate.
with a pin or needle (Sinner)
not a knife

water carrier ~~decorates~~ decorates

2 or 3 bushes in a month.
20 - 30 a year.

Tail tomorrow
about 2 to a day, } he gets
1 water carrier }
2 to a day } water
1 to a day } wedger
He is the only mirror.

winter people go to blots
get wet beneath a year
works on blades work for company

Manual labour Brain Wires

It is ~~not~~ ^{not} ~~not~~ ^{not} ~~not~~ ^{not} ~~not~~ ^{not}
 ok - the ~~same~~

They do cycle every day, 200/ft

This was 2 days work 54/ft

Tomorrow finished the jobs

24 days total

4

15 days a month the work

~~15~~
~~63~~
~~95~~

sent 4 towns a mile

They were now 101 a mile

200 fots = ~~200~~ 100 a month

4 days work the is 54/ft

If they finish today, they 3 days

about 2 hours after mt beating
 finished starts again

30 repeats + 100 good

made them down total amount

he says the vehicles

he says he gets about 21

1211 1 town a day for each of 2
 earth carries.

who use also the 'earth carries

with 15. bottom

4 hours all the help and other 5 in all

! am to carry earth
 depending on kind of work!

7 x 15 = 105 Tonnes + 4 or 8 etc

water carrier also keep record books out before 2:30 this they get them.

out of 50 throw 5-10 at broken in beating

They are designed for use on tripod. Cursed bottom = means that you can move the top to pour water lifting the bottom + also air can circulate all around.

he said of 1 that broke 'nam' two right.

he sells these + distribute cash on to workers

29 25 spins spin hole with ash in it smooths - 30:03 = 6 min 5 1/2 min all 5:10 sec,

this work is done on these ~~pieces~~

I have not seen water do it, get he has gone to lunch.

hard way is much easier

but as breaks bottom

7 x 15 = 105 Tonnes + 4 or 8 etc
 210 12.2 / 2 22
 [300] 24.30
 30.30

water corner also keep;
 record leakage out before 2:3
 this they wet them.

out of 50 throw 5-10 at
 broken in beating

they are designed for ~~one~~ force
 on tripod curved bottom
 = means that you can
 move the top to pour water
 lifting the bottom + also air can
 circulate all around.

he said of 1 that broke 'nam'
 7 two raft

he sells these + distribute cash on
 side to workmen

29 25 spins in hole with ash
 in it smooths - 30:03.
 2. ~~6~~ spins 5 1/2 min - all
 5.10 sec,

this work is done on these ~~three~~ pieces

I have not seen water do it, just
 he has gone to lunch.

hard way is much easier

but as breaks bottom

new work stop
he makes planned / have better

34 to 5 lined up to be read better

he has 2 holes. the ground
saddles it

2nd beating, the begin by using
water the add ash today.

but he wets it.

he says 34 is one day
+ 2 for as they are working on

day before is lined up 17

he puts it -> finished at 5320
- 5 25
a here 36 + 17 for 5 - all.

5-335
5915

20 people to 5
independent operation

ways of everyone or they related.

he does not put extra lump of clay
inside at start or ~~do~~ does.
3x he put ash inside

clay preparation by ~~series~~ is now
going on outside

7 HAN & SHU
wife -> I think cousin

Man in from artist

brother of father. Son

the father was master

clay separator gets start of
puddling piece + does it with
foot + then puts into pot again.

puddling hole depth is

then cuts off with lad +
throws back. ground prepared
with soft dirt from sieve

but they beat the lump with both
of them they ~~are~~ sieve

but by the small earth-hole +
leave till next day.

after he has thrown up + puddles
foot. after this thrown on clay
clay from rare place.

The Man earth into middle

55

cover up the hole with wood
leaves + clay.

roof made ~~of~~ of clay alone.

1 for door.

+ 4 for roof
+ also pots on roof

pots out.

14 x 8 + 1. ~~14 x 8~~

They say they will fire tomorrow
are better full.

8 days the dry.

next puddling

1 puddling this is for 20 hours

4 days ~~is~~ using 3 kloo

put on 4 jars

16 Nov 11 hrs 3

stacked tops of
no air holes

150 x 75

 120 x 95

4 put on then he puts crafty pots
to cover the top as another
begins to smoke

padding hole basket lined
up. 72 x 28

leats up earth with a piece of
20 cm long ed.

Lots left = pile.

$$\begin{array}{r} 17 \times 3 \quad 51 \\ 39 \quad \quad 39 = 80 \text{ lbs} \\ \hline 80 \end{array}$$

3 v fire decor. They put on broods
v ~~small~~ empty cat:

They make up.
4.30 now

c 15 messages begin for

wheel is put over fly wheel as for

but they fill padding hole with
c 10 units heavy stuff

padding hole only lined with clay
when no one there.

By 4.52¹² he is travelling in
erratically 4 bales in.

padding clay is only big stuff

5.07.

about 4 feet: 4 Binnis 1 vent

he says now 8.

fill up padding hole then cover with
water.

Get the hole to put end of stick in

① he was on one at ~~307~~ 07

3 12 he will be finished

② 12.20

end of the hole says 10

10. end of 10. 16. $\frac{1}{2}$

How many will be made today

he calls it to 12

ended at 19

metal shaft of wheel. no ⑬

ended at 22.20

no ⑭ finished at 26 25.

no ⑮ finished at 31 55

no 16 " " 37.30 (any)
no 17 " " 42 (16)

no be started for this c 4 30

he looks with it foot + rest left on bar.

no 15 will take more time as he is cutting off shavings

all this time flaws coming from shavings

no Today I ran shavings \$2 ran on earth.

1 carrying water

1 wedging one hatting

They are using judding hole fill

It looks right to get 2 chaises loads a day

at end of all bathing drying
on end, 51 pots.

2 hours over ~~57.00~~ 40.00

white is good water on top.
side of white water hole.

he rows 2 more.

old man watching top.

downy man has brought 2 loads
he also spreads it out.

ten huddle 45 40
he cleans up.

1 huddle hole full surely

7:35 she has stopped
potting + looks again

and evening has cracked

last huddle - slowly

franked stoking at 51.25.

findling kept lots of to wall
stuff on top.

It no put below boards

54:35. begin to cover over
the hole - great lump crap beside

he had said that 16 huddles go on.
the stokes! told me.

I suppose he needs heat so great that
all air is burnt off top no quite
little

he didn't cover bird entrance
with palm fronds

but with metal thing from
wheelbarrow.

he made 30 pots today
& only used $\frac{1}{2}$ the puddled clay
rest left for today under
Lasparkin

Tomorrow morning they take about
tomorrow they do puddle
& day after they start
1 hour. 6 they start.

no work for crop

is at least here & gone to village

on sticks 8 — 8

8 — 8

8 — 8

8 — 8

8 +
8 6 8

370
48
6

30
64
6
100 at least

he says
90

he says 4 henk
almost none

carried to village

wood comes go round village
to village

too close to flea markets

they pack top as flea market

8.4 meters at bottom

always use meters
few at top

ask from market

~~cannot to as long, but not hole~~

to villages

to store

1 to a day to sell pots

5 days a week
(1 month's collection is 2 hrs work) } 1 to day

2 days for selling

5 mats

1 to run them, carry 2 of them

30. for a fringe is important

10 small poles of 6 each are being made, 1 of 4

1 of wood carries that the price he gets paid for that.

arg 1 to sell

20 years ago was in this place

4 years old destroyed him +

his older

8 years a week
going for 20 years

each go to Dih Bary

liby at end of funny only palan

runes of paper + other fatter

no use for donkey craft ✓

how is it sold to Jagan ✓

next good desert go to BIKARI ✓

64 to Dih Bary

8

so 30 will they be sold elsewhere ✓

~~200 + 200 of ...~~

~~do we need to get to ...~~

~~... is not ...~~

~~...~~

he thinks about 3,000 people

+ 1500 hours [unusual]

to 1 take to Bikan

~~...~~ I go to Jagan by donkey

goes however to Bikan with us they cannot sell.

but palan fronds last because easier to get through entrance.

BAKER FAKARI

he is older.

باقر فاری

باقر فاری

MAHMUD	father BAKER ALI
	father JAFFAR
	father ALI

~~SHOLLA KUNAR~~
~~BARBAR ALI~~
~~MUHAMMAD~~ ~~BARBAR ALI~~
the father's brother

SAYAHAI

water
cousin
old man

Not old man. HASSAN →
DARVISH (father's name)

no relation.

old
man

beater

father KUNAR

~~KUNAR~~ ~~RAHIM~~

name MUHAMMAD,
MOLLA KUNAR,
brother of father.

wedger.

HEDAR AHMAD, RAHIMI
father of HEDAR AHMAD RAHIMI

his son cousin of owner.

AHMANA mother FAKHRI

father AHMAD
~~father ALY his father~~

AHMANA is ~~brother~~
mother

belong AHMADI
is AC I FAKH

beater.

MUHAMMAD & ALI FAKHRI

↓ brother of boys.

GHOLAM → wood carrier
+ earth getter.

GHOLAM . ~~AKHAR~~ HEDAR

ISA AHMADI.
related to Hedar AHMAD
RAHIMI wood carrier

cousins.

he put wood into bins.

only 2 wood carrier.

Gholan Hed.
Hosun Darnik } carried
wa Ahnadi } earth
Hedar Ahnadi }

~~HAA~~
~~father ISA CAMBAR~~
~~mother MARIAM.~~
~~father ISA AHMADI~~
~~father CAMBAR~~
they dont know.

ISA Carubar. 20th
carnel:

75
beater in his brother
wedger is

O'Holan Nedon

→ father takes to ask.

✓
futte. Ali

✓
entloze
brother not entloze) " "

~~BoF~~ F.B.S. old. cas Rahimi (far)

no relatives ^{same} Hedar Rahimi (")

Rahimi "

Rahimi

~~Rahimi~~ Ahmadi.

Permanent staff

✓
Gaber Fakari ياوقنى ياوقنى

✓
Mukhod ali . لا x ياوقنى

✓
mahand (Kuro) (father name) ياوقنى

✓
Cholan (Hedar) ياوقنى

✓
Blasan (darruk) (father) ياوقنى

✓
Hedar (Ahmood) ياوقنى

✓
tra. (CAMIBAK) ياوقنى

7 people.

called house KAN IMI

lot a fancy bond.

GHOLAM AHMADI

ISA
C AMBAR
AHMADI

GHOLAM MEDAR

HASAN ABAS, RAHIMI

MUHAMMAD Gholam "

Sia. Horein. " Rahimi
Moharrat Laruban → family of
Baker

Ali Gholam — SADIQI

→ only 5: the network

81
does not know father or mother

same family
→ father is brother of Hasan's father.

~~KUNAR KANTAI~~

This morning juddling + also beating
at moment only him + old man

MAURU, 3.

Q 19

230 Khammar,

310 Mauru 1

300 Qaleh Qirin

late on ridge of gravel stone
fields c 20 x 25 m.

S.E. is a village c 300 m,
lighter colour mud mes c.
1 m on top.

Qaleh KUMIS

Q 22

top is 45 faces + 100 out

outside set c 360 faces + 200

late crop.

Q23 Sultan Miri

25

castle mes c ~~30~~ 30 m.
main walls around whole site
c 3m + real walls stand c 7m on
top in mud/BB.
on date lozh wide part of it. +
fields below. dark above

Mauru 4 Q20

bears 350° to bridge

bears 295 to bridge on rd S

long dimension S to c 300 m
from 175

dark shaley real mound. the
from mt's several by stone lines
not dressed but more than 1
course visible

~~250~~ faces c 250 proway
on basis 320. low shaley

Q25

T. ZIARAT (washed ground)

17 P. 300
226 faces ~~250~~ flat stones (crab)

ind way between village + 12

c 150 m from edge to village ^{100 to} 12
120 to river at closest.

beas 310 to 12 + 180 to village

flat. fallen trees + rocks
galvanization x stones
x 12

Jetstone Zarat is to North

area, c 50+50 m.
round size. 120 x 120 faces.
ht c 4m.
no water around nor any trees or
vegetation

rough of water gas coming from Mt

from corner of mound 531 affaces
x 142. sporadic pottery scatters.
to the East.

~~52~~ faces sq nite edge c 120 yds
from river
close to river + some wells around.

2nd at 2. hilly + late across
river ^{Q26} from 2nd at bears ~~150~~ 150°
+ c 50 x 80 m. on top of a bluff

HISSAR I then road
bears 230° to 3.
~~40~~ 40° to 2nd at
250° to Damashur.
~~Q27~~ Q28

size + ht as main.
~~must be well at foot otherwise~~
jungle but on S side
1 small field. hitch for
at least 1/2 miles to any settlement.
no water.

1 very fat
blanc stuff + lot of confus
to top. Unresolvable tree on top.

~~Q28~~ Q29

③ 12 130 + 140 (MP) ht c 3 1/2 m
no cultivation around it bears 230°
from I. are very patchy
dusty white S F c 800 m from I
no water settlement or fields.

② mid way between 2 + 3 hills
c 10 m sq + c 1 ht lots of markers
+ frags of vitrified brick lining

~~Q29~~ Q30

by craggy rocks sparsely
over c ~~100~~ 100 m x 70 m
between 1 + 2 + a little glass perhaps
should be added to Sars from ①
call it 4. v v non-descript on flat
ground. Q31

W+S

Ziarat Daniel to ~~SSE~~ of Ziarat

or. to alluvium

Q ~~32~~ 32

Q ~~33~~ 33. ~~horizontal~~.
27 Ziarat ~~the~~

220 + 270. K116

K117 no shell

71 → N mountain }
 200 → to K117 }
 from edge of mud flats. }
 50m + 40 + 1ht next done,
 less than 700m from K117
 200, 600m or 550m. K118

K118 1/2 finished eladon
 1 late reworked
 2 speckled green blue on top
 3 light " " " " "
 1 reworked hand made.
 c 400m from hills. no shell
 on S end of log done - area c 50m
 + 50m. bears 135° to 117
 on N end of log done 1/2 to shore

K119 bears 30° to K116
 c 110 to K118.
 on N end of dune 180 + 75 hours
 saddle of 2 m dunes 2 m high

of stone + bricks + a lot of pottery
no shell, a real site on the edge
dunes - dunes

c.c. 500 m to K116

c.c. 600 m to K118

K120 bears 240° + c.c. 700 m to K116
1950 to K119 + c.c. 700 m

= middle of line of dunes to shell with
vegetation. good dense pottery.
spreads 62
600 m + mt of 270.

all from SA 2nd
in by direction of site - S

North bears 343° to W end of
Bonza big site
+ is c.c. 200 m from edge of palm
trees

This line of dunes is off flodable dunes

site is on dunes some areas v concentrated
but mostly not so but shells everywhere

K121. in middle of sand dunes
mostly c. 3 m high, stuff but a 250
good bit of pottery v yonaduc are c. 300
+ 100 m

bears c. 150° to by Bonza site +
pal. 1 km SW

c. 400 m North is K122 which = K100
150 m + 120.

K123

93 to Mt

150 to Bonza site K97.

bears due ^{south} ~~west~~ to K122.

+ bears 67° to K121.

+ c.c. 150 m

set another road dune c. 150 m + 120 ²⁰⁰

it is c. 700 m to north of K116

K124 = rest of drive of K 119
750 m + 150 wide roads K119 as
N at north end.

drive runs

E side edge of drive c 50 m is border
of foliage. Drive has lots of foliage + some
bricks.

10° bears up N from middle

140 hu " S "

80 to water

352 to K 97

drive runs c 3m of road into

=

K125. near BANZA.

flat site on gravel of high gravel terrace
c 400 m from last palm trees
before sudden descent.

low S most part of village c 250 m W
of main market + 30° to W end

115 hu

93

of K 97 is 170m + 80 reported from K126
↳ 50m just with blastic rocks

K126 on top of gravel terrace
+ runs ~~into~~ ^{into 125} end is c 150m
Merua direction from Mosque
~~to 125~~

200 Terrace + 183 faces

K127 bears 79° to + 3 on K130
c 310° to BANZA on edge of high land
no palms

stone + bricks as area c 90 + 50 faces
clearly reveal little houses rather than
a large mound. Not high is c 80 cm
rock from number ie + 3 but north from
• rocky level rocky beach rocks

K128 128

72 nte 220m

94 then 200m

16 then 240m

40

nte begins 220m

then 200m hitch then 240m nte

110° to Unwayu

333° to ?

back bearing 160° from 12 on North
end

both ntes are mounds of sand with
moss + some bits of island with hills
between

re ht sc 220m + 70

+ read sc 240m + 70

record has little pottery

ntes are between one line of hills + dunes
road leads to E + hills to West

K129 on top of A dunes

no dateable pottery, generally modern

K131 is 125° to K1 on edge of dunes
110° in village + c 400m
crappy but with bricks + c 40 + 30%

K 130 is Galat: Saravan,

(A1)
 K 130.D. bear. 9° to saddle: central
 mound + distance
 + 42° to rocky $\square$ mt. $45 - 44\frac{1}{2}$
 + 83° to $\square$ with base on. $\times 3$

line of mt.

pit c 50 m in ground pottery lane from
 west with ash etc 40 paces

5 60 m from lee to saddle:
 central mound.

central road K 130 E m 260 paces
 on bear, $10^\circ + 220$ Matha paces
 red mounds covered - red pot one kiln bearing

+ pieces of mounds ground an eroded mounds
 $18m \times 9m$

$$\begin{array}{r} \boxed{\times 4} - \times 1 - 263^\circ \\ - \times 2 \quad ? \\ - \times 3 \quad \boxed{292} \end{array}$$

$\times 2 - \times 1$	$\times 3 - \times 1 - 225$
$\times 2 - \times 3 - 139$	$\times 2 - 329$
$\times 4$	$\times 4 - 113^\circ$

K130F is mens. 148 + 110 mls

39-64 89-

hook 2 2 1/4 one side 3 cm

protrudes 40 cm

width 5 1/2 cm thick

72 1/2 x 4

22 x 3

308 x 1.

other 97 x at least 120. walls c2-3m

bit in ~~straw~~ area of shell
middle of x shell. collected
sample.

c. 50 x 30 faces = shells + low hula

from F in separate block + one catch
No

129 + 1 | 270°
100 x 3 | 345 + 150m
75 x 2. A circled number '7' is to the right.

direction of x3

172 +1 (10)
 150 +3 abstract as +2 we are
 along 200m for new edge of +2.

X 4 ~~154~~ 154 (11)
 +3 183 by 12 on
 +2 215
 note A collection here + towards +2

~~+4~~ = 20
 from here on is burrows. line is c
 180m here 1 small road

(13) 149 +4
 195 +3
 244 +2
 162 +4
 242 ~~179~~ +3
 (14) 268 +2
 172 +4
 (15) 250 +1
 275 +3
 80m at
 235m +4
 (16)

+4 - +1 is 261° to +2 is c 300 101
 to +3 is 291
 +4 is 120m on bearing 80° from +4
 80° ←

+3 is 100m
 +1 is c 250m down the slope
 250m
 on bearing c 50°

(17) 61 +4
 344 +3
 283 +1

(18) 31 +4
 345 +3 rather an isolated hill
 312 +1

19 50 +4 near burrow mounds.
 27 +3
 18 +1

$165 + 4 = 20$
 $197 + 3$
 $220 + 2$
 reatched top on edge of village

$188 + 4$
 $238 + 3$
 gorge: village divi 21

K128

350 m x 70. mud bluff - ht 100 + 70
 on N end of line clay dune rises
 1 1/2 m above floodable daskit.
 eroded clay soil dam walls

231° to khazim
 247 along dune to ht palms

K132. bears 400 m + R3.20
 to ~~to~~ horn of Khazim, in
 role of dune 50 + 50 faces

2 crafts (tong) / sub glazed thorn

1 late reatched
 32

~~208~~
~~48~~

K133 260m + 65 faces.
 just misc 1m above spring tide work
 145° long dune
 04° to khazim + thargun. of beach J81
 lots of pottery.
 small 20 m between 2 rounds.

~~Salt~~ Nakhla tower, c 100 m
 + ccc 18 hrs.
 cc 160° to village with mangroves
~~to khazim~~ K134 c 4.7 hrs from 134

K134 late B + W etc on eroded
 by boats lots of dam walls beside road
 110° to khazim

modern b+w etc / morecraft
 must be record thargun of same of
 1 ba.

135 road dune 70 + 40 tons
dune + a little pottery

325 bangle

257 K bangle 2

in dark

K136 dead flat site. 200m x 7.

28° to 1

160° to Bahari + ~~550m~~ 550m.

S ~~end~~ of site dark + fallen trees
around Bahari.

K 137 550m long x 120.

shelly mounds

c 160° to east of Bahari. ~~4000m~~ 3900

2 1/2 m ht

M abson village.

c 295 from village of Bahari

which is 4000m from BAHMANI

K138 hears from Ned

350m along dune 326°.

322° to site

11° to + 3m K130

on high left side of dunes + small
gravel heaps to E

width

150° to K until ~~at 400m~~
cc 400m.

370m wide

Somewhat deep

K 139

332° to Kumit

1950 to Sinteri

to S of little zorat grass -
area of 80 x ~~100~~ ¹⁰⁰ ~~100~~ ¹⁰⁰ faces thick shell
protrusion of 90° low ¹⁰⁰ m saddle.

Palms to N + E at c 100 m

236 to Khargan bunnak

c 195° from K ~~to~~ ^{to} Khargan
+ c 400 m

K 140.

258 to Khargan bunnak

130 to Sinteri

hitchy mud misc c 1 1/2 m between
Sinteri + a nearby bit of palms.

c 180 x ~~100~~ ¹⁰⁰ ~~100~~ ¹⁰⁰ m

to north modern stuff on dunes
leading towards bit site of
yesterday.

K 141 B

107

K 141

-Tep Majban of earlier unit.

bears - 132° to village of MA JBUN.

272° to All Metri

on edge of Sand dune. Concentration of shells
misc 1m

Shell matter extends roughly
no right of Margheri way

220 x 170 μ concentrated, v concentrated
on side of dune.

extends along dune sporadically, rest of
land along dune edge is 700m x 250.
not all is wash

by washed SF much must be

Sand is ~~400~~ 300 from head of Margheri
way

c 8m

c 30m ht.

300m to ①

82 x 4

43 x 3

04 x 2

250 faces

cliff edge

K130.

center = middle

3 1/2
5 1/4

beams N-S

31 + 12 North faces

lid with mounds

Traces of fabrications and stone

lie of rock, pinnacles between 1+4

valley rock very eroded

beams 235° c 40 faces

1 small ridge

eroded off

between 200 by at center

9 x 2 1/2 structural

2 big brick construction none gatch

K 142 50 + ~~40~~ 70 faces on
flat dotted trees all around.
put across in use Tombac +
Chelo roads divide.

flat eroded clay dirt.
c 200 m + 60° to village

~~98 50 + 65 = 115~~
~~95 - 35 = 60~~

~~300 m + 250 m~~
~~350 m~~

K 143

300 m + 250 m mounds - low wall

~~350 m~~ 350 m sq.
red with bits of bricks. wall on
stones / red yellow sand stone +
also some beach rock no volcanic
fairly regular floor
none plate floor - for walls

most unplantered.

bricks rings
see with cross prying

19 + 4 1/2

21 x 5

24 x 5 1/4

6 1/2 left side m

The normal is generally 2-3.

other one is rather small.

note bear 274 to Delu.

353 to Chelo

28

12 Sans beam

c 5 m ht.

near by across stream - 2 m high
gravel + mid terrace 180 + 80 face
graves on top with reared bricks + a
few long sans beam + modern
sheds used all come from graves

K144
- terminal drainage channel between
beams to 40° .

so covered with grass log debris in
 $\sim 115^\circ$

+ starts c 150 m from K143

181/248/340/357.8

~~181-323~~ Total length = 1250 m
 $\frac{650}{20}$

latest stuff is Int. ~~700m~~ 600m
collection. K145A.

K145B is ~~to~~ west 450 m.

K146 is far end

159° from E end to middle of K143

285° down long depression of side

~~450~~ 450 m from K143

43 $\frac{1}{2}$ hectares

113

at c 1000 it is 490 m across

at c 900 m it is 700 m across

at c 600 it is 450 m

at c 300 it is ~~500~~ 500 m

from c 150 - 450 west of the
= covered - road + high embankment

W end is 1100 m from side of
Tape Deck by Transit - beam 110° from

K147

K147.

$\frac{46}{2}$ $\frac{158}{70}$
7' 70m

one is 120 m + 70.

other is 180 ~~+~~ + 120 - beam 80° to beam

runs N-S to c 80 m from Transit

K147 growing out of flat desert
on edge of palm trees of Dehn village
fly, warat

2 areas

1.8 hrs - direction $\approx 93^\circ$ from Dehn

K148

on edge of village bears 270° to
village + to stop road that
to Dehn. marks 1.5 m ht near
Nanabi. car area $\approx 70 + 50$ m
 $\approx 130^\circ$

This is Dehn of earliest Dehn mts

K149 on edge of hill of Dehn palm
trees + desert.

extracted 310° to Dehn ^{middle}
small ~~target~~ ^{warat} on top of mte.
400 + 100 along palm which
bear 150°

~~K150 on edge of line of Dehn palm
leaves 50 to K149 + estimated 680m
marking on line of road of edge of
hill or on area 100m wide ≈ 26 height
very nearby~~

K150 + 151

1075 m from K151 to
700 m $\rightarrow 45^\circ$

up 30 ft by road 1.5 m
280 m.

ht is ≈ 600 m + ~~320~~ 320

then ≈ 300 m + 280.

not in light

seen up to ≈ 100 m from village

+ a strip alongside

K152

670 m from Zorat + bears to it
+ 360° ± 200 m from 2 towers:

palm trees -

by Yoradi's pottery on flat dirt.

~~200 m~~ ± 100 m by

K153. 350 m to Zorat bear 34°S

+ 170 m from edge to K152 bear 200

300 m x 150: flat dirt
a nice flat off pottery

K154 (1) bears to 25° to Zorat

248 Maugh

230 bulge kerhi.

- dirt site near 70 m from lot of
pottery some bricks etc

white gravelly soil clams nice above sandy
dirt

300 x 900. ends 1/2 m

long diameter 210°

from ~~pottery~~ north towards Zorat

E ~~end~~ end bears 320° ± 150 m to

K150

end 200 m + 300 m 154 B

with Selgutz + a few m. all
picked up not all late Sgraff picked up

K 155.

137 ~~Front of~~ Deh 300
356. Mangh Bala + c 30 ~~100m~~

to South + E of the Zarat
K 156 to Mangh
c c 195 ~~to~~ Mangh Kashi

note is eroding out of a line of
road on which Zarat stands
+ is c 150 m + 30 in size
// to palm trees

K 156. bears 25° + c ~~200~~ 100 m to Mangh Bala
bears 255° to Mangh Poon
a flat dakt

limit is near village note has lots
of shell note is c 200 x 70 m

K 157

bears 45° 12' of K 155 + c 300 m
+ 300 m from Mangh Bala bears 350
Point bears 265

modern grass on top
mat 110 paces + 200 m in diam.
+ is c 100 m from edge of river

320 m to next note by river bank at
c 50 x 50 m

K 158. 40 cm ~~also~~ long along
river bed + 150 m up river bank from
small note 50 x 50 which is 320
m from ~~K 157~~ K 157. note is
mat 120 m wide + ends c 50
m before K 10.

long dimension bears 95°
short concentrated - strip 75 m
wide along river

also = dakt tower of village of Bala
+ 50 m long, ~~100 x 70 m~~ 150 x 50

struff part - with 157.

K159 on edge of river + edge of
Bombay palm trees to East of a road
165° to E end of gravel Terrace of

Bouza
267 to Mangh
river plain partly irrigated about 2 hrs
wide ca 120 x 80
+ little to North of road 40 x 40

K160 is really part of the 1/2 K142
river site. it is separated by 120
yards of new palm field. bears
45° to other site

12 5 fms across at 25 pm &
120 m long | have lots + no do last
50. /

v

K 103

	A	B
30	edge of road	136 / 96 1/2 +
31		145 / 104 +

32 getting

The getting is below water but
lands late lots of reeds

32	149 / 115 +
33	169 / 126 +

330° creek not by
33 + 34 no holes

34 mound 15 ft away
 182 1/2 / 142 1/2 +
 c25 ft for edge

36 c15 ft away
 B A
 160 181 +
 62 buildings

37 end of hill
 creek
 370 → 50m
 +
 37 B A
 167-190 +

38 close to mound B
 A
 189 156 +
 mound

A B
194 / 152 $\neq$

→ (38)
A

30 ft
+

less 180° + 30 ft
another 20 ft

39 - road c 340 m feet

(39) A B
183 127 X

(40) at the corner between 39 + 40

about 20 ft into line
+ 20 ft S of 40

+ 10 ft from road
181 III X

c 100 m along road

+ vls c 50 ft from wall

70° + 50 m (circle) c 10 + 10

rocks in creek were to
 little 10x10
 bears 3 10° to get it

on road in 61 hours for wall.

rocks ran led

1 creek at 110°
 B A
 112 + 145

roughly ran down

34 10
 34 10

High point 154 feet +
45° from A

A	B	
142	-73	(60)
175	-75	(61)

Le A B -45 from B
edge of woods

(295)	02	(62)
-------	----	------

High part of site 0817

28-37

40-51

57-73

390 15 x 3 94-115

High Johnson ballok

20 2 1/2 of ground level

K130

214 x1
334 x2
91 x3

40

forward end of late rounded
rite.

c 40 feet down to rock outcrop

low rock outcrop to (+)

rock bedding on ridge c ~~40~~ + 40 feet
40 + 35

late rhyolite + claston

~~42~~
41

100 2
124 x3
162 +1

5A

little dip end of ridge

160° to base ridge rock bedding

c 120m

+ another 50 feet c 320°
from it

(42) marked w/ds

maps to 41.

$\underbrace{\quad \quad \quad}_{+x2}$

(4) 0 0 0

0

77 +2

113 +3

158 +1

(42)

180 fto 4

120

80 fto 200

~~63 / 74 / 35~~

63 / 74 / 35

w/ds 18 1/2 + 19

INDEX of SITES

QALATU		D 17	1-3
SHIWU	I	D 15	4
SHIWU	2	D 16	5-6
MOGHUN(S)	1A+B+C+D	D 14	7-10
NERAN	I	D 10	11-12
NERAN	2	D 11	11-12 12-13
NERAN	3	D 12	14
NERAN	4	D 13	15-16
BOROGLA	A, B, C, D	D 18	18-19
BOROGLA	2	D 19	19
BOSTANU(S)	1	D 20	21
BOSTANU(S)	2	D 21	21
BOSTANU(S)	3	D 22	21

Surjan - Heran / TRGS. XLII / 202
 SAADUTABAD, KHON - SURKH
 MAS HIZ, BAGHIN / HERMAN

S Heran asat tohda 1905 h 1243-
 dunnar, cairi Pds waldy, Sutan.

Goldsmidt 1873 TRGS. h 65
 D Almas to Serdin - Heran

Heran - Kayd - Surjan - Bgt.
 TRGS h 1841 / 136

TRGS 1867 Goldsmid Heran - Kayd
 - Chah B abar.
 Plojer wex floret Bohubilin
 Heran - Kayd

زئبور - wash.

Sharon - Bayan.

Zarabur

dilid ~~pas~~ ~~tas~~

dachmanas gues

BELLER

M T R O BALAN

شیراز کاشرات

9 70 lot 26 17 Teker.

Fangot Laney

juo = fly (magas)

4/00

- 400

100

1100m.
x 110° from K47.

K 245

hadisatijah ~~ultra~~

